

Correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by benzimidazolium dichromate – A kinetic and mechanistic aspects

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The oxidation of a number of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols by benzimidazolium dichromate (BIDC), in dimethyl sulphoxide, leads to the formation of the corresponding benzaldehydes. The reaction is first order with respect to each BIDC and alcohol. The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions and the dependence has the form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of [1,1-²H₂]benzyl alcohol exhibited the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect. The rates of the oxidation of *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols correlated best with Taft's σ_1 and σ_{R}^0 constants. The *para*-substituted compounds exhibited excellent correlation with σ_1 and $\sigma_{\text{R}}^{\text{BA}}$ values. The polar reaction constants are negative. The rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol was determined in nineteen organic solvents. An analysis of the solvent effect by multiparametric equations indicated the greater importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvents. Suitable mechanisms have been discussed.

Keywords: Kinetics, mechanism, correlation analysis, oxidation, benzyl alcohol, benzimidazolium dichromate.

Introduction

Selective oxidation of organic compounds under non-aqueous conditions is an important transformation in synthetic organic chemistry. For this purpose, a number of different chromium(VI) derivatives have been reported¹⁻⁵. In 1998, Meng *et al.*⁶ reported a new Cr^{VI} derivative – benzimidazolium dichromate (BIDC). It is neither hygroscopic nor light sensitive, therefore, it is more stable and easily stored as compared to other Cr^{VI} reagents. We have been interested in the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation by BIDC and so far few reports on the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by BIDC are published from our laboratory⁷⁻¹⁴. The substrates used for the studies were aliphatic secondary alcohols⁷, oxyacids of phosphorus⁸, aliphatic primary alcohols⁹, formic and oxalic acids¹⁰, aliphatic aldehydes¹¹, dialkyl and diphenyl sulfides¹², DL-methionine¹³, and alkyl phenyl sulfides¹⁴. A perusal of literature showed that the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by BIDC has not been reported yet. In this paper, the kinetics and correlation analyses of organic reactivity in the oxidation of some mono-

substituted *para*- and *meta*-benzyl alcohols by BIDC in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent is described. The mechanistic aspects are discussed.

This is justified to report here the results of the kinetic study of the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols^{7,9} by BIDC (Table 1). This will help the reader to understand the differences observed between the kinetics of aliphatic alcohols and that of substituted benzyl alcohols.

Results and discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

The oxidation of benzyl alcohols resulted in the formation of the corresponding benzaldehydes. The product analysis and the stoichiometry determination suggested the following overall reaction:

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Table 1. The results of the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by BIDC

Sl. No.	Parameter	Primary alcohol ⁹	Secondary alcohol ⁷
1.	Stoichiometry	1(BIDC) : 3(alcohol)	1(BIDC) : 3(alcohol)
2.	Oxidation product	Aldehyde	Ketone
3.	Order w.r.t. BIDC	One	One
4.	Order w.r.t. alcohol	Two	More than one but less than two
5.	Order w.r.t. [H ⁺]	Two	Two
6.	Kinetic isotope effect	5.90 at 298 K	4.99 at 298 K
7.	Solvent effect	Cation solvation played major role	Cation solvation played major role
8.	Correlation analysis	Excellent correlation with Pavelich-Taft equation	Excellent correlation with Pavelich-Taft equation
9.	Oxidizing species	Doubly protonated BIDC	Doubly protonated BIDC

The reaction is of first order with respect to BIDC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants do not depend on the initial concentration of BIDC (Table 1). The reaction is of first order with respect to the alcohol also (Table 2).

Table 2. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by BIDC at 298 K

[Alcohol] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ [BIDC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
0.10	1.0	0.0	75.4
0.20	1.0	0.0	155
0.30	1.0	0.0	230
0.40	1.0	0.0	305
0.50	1.0	0.0	368
0.70	1.0	0.0	520
1.00	1.0	0.0	762
0.20	2.0	0.0	161
0.20	3.0	0.0	151
0.20	5.0	0.0	149
0.20	7.0	0.0	158
0.20	2.0	0.0	150 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions and the dependence is of the form: $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 3). A plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺] is linear ($r^2 = 0.9989$) with an intercept on the rate-ordinate (Fig. 1). The magnitude of the intercept matches

Table 3. Dependence of the reaction rate on the hydrogen-ion concentration

[Benzyl alcohol] = 0.2 mol dm ⁻³ , [BIDC] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ , T = 298 K	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)						
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.8	1.0	1.5
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	336	505	703	1000	1630	2000	2860

Fig. 1. A plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺] indicating $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$, [BIDC] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³; [benzyl alcohol] = 0.2 mol dm⁻³; T = 298 K.

well with the value of rate constant obtained under same conditions (Table 1). The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent another acid dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BIDC (2) to

yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile. Formation of protonated B IDC has earlier been postulated in the oxidation of methionine by B IDC¹³.

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by B IDC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. In blank experiments, with the alcohol absent, no noticeable consumption of B IDC was observed. The addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate of oxidation (Table 2). This indicates that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was

observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively. BHT is an excellent trap for free radicals¹⁵. The fact that BHT was recovered unchanged also goes against the occurrence of a one electron oxidation. The oxidation of [1,1-²H₂]benzyl alcohol (PhCD₂OH) by B IDC exhibited a substantial kinetic isotope effect (Table 3).

The rates of oxidation of all monosubstituted alcohols by B IDC were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 4).

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by B IDC was studied in nineteen organic solvents. The solubility of the reactants and the reaction of B IDC with primary and secondary alcohols limited the choice of solvents. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of the rate constant, *k*₂, are recorded in Table 5.

Table 4. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by B IDC

Subst.	<i>k</i> ₂ × 10 ⁵ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger at 298 K (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	305	762	890	4630	66.5±0.8	-63±3	85.0±0.6
<i>p</i> -Me	580	1390	3320	7750	63.3±0.7	-69±2	85.0±0.6
<i>p</i> -OMe	1730	3820	8560	19000	58.3±0.9	-77±3	81.0±0.7
<i>p</i> -Cl	173	431	1090	2950	69.2±1.7	-58±6	86.4±1.2
<i>p</i> -Br	155	395	1010	2740	70.1±1.5	-56±5	86.6±1.2
<i>p</i> -F	400	938	2280	5780	65.2±1.6	-65±5	84.5±1.3
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	16.1	46.0	133	440	81.0±2.4	-37±7	91.9±1.9
<i>p</i> -COOMe	61.0	159	432	1230	73.6±1.8	-52±5	88.8±1.4
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	42.3	119	330	982	77.0±1.6	-43±3	89.6±1.3
<i>p</i> -CN	58.1	158	431	1220	74.6±1.4	-49±4	88.9±1.1
<i>p</i> -SMe	575	1320	3150	7570	62.9±1.3	-70±4	83.6±1.0
<i>p</i> -NHAc	598	1440	3410	8190	63.8±0.9	-67±3	83.5±0.7
<i>m</i> -Me	574	1360	3260	7780	63.6±1.0	-67±3	83.6±0.8
<i>m</i> -OMe	415	945	2360	5880	64.9±1.7	-66±5	84.4±1.3
<i>m</i> -Cl	69.6	178	505	1370	73.4±1.6	-51±5	88.5±1.3
<i>m</i> -Br	64.9	165	470	1290	73.6±1.8	-51±5	88.7±1.4
<i>m</i> -F	86.0	215	600	1620	72.3±1.7	-54±5	88.1±1.4
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	6.08	18.2	61.5	170	82.8±1.3	-39±4	94.2±1.0
<i>m</i> -CF ₃	22.5	64.5	194	550	78.8±1.1	-42±4	91.1±0.9
<i>m</i> -CN	38.0	105	307	840	76.3±1.1	-46±3	89.9±0.9
<i>m</i> -SMe	197	482	1260	3220	68.5±1.4	-59±3	86.1±1.1
<i>m</i> -NHAc	210	514	1320	3380	68.0±1.4	-61±4	86.0±1.1
<i>m</i> -NH ₂	1030	2240	5150	12100	60.0±1.5	-75±4	82.3±1.2
<i>m</i> -OPh	153	375	1030	2690	70.6±1.6	-55±5	86.7±1.3
PHCD ₂ OH	46.1	123	326	831	70.9±0.7	-63±2	89.6±0.5

Table 5. Effect of solvent on the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by B IDC at 298 K

Solvent	$k_2 \times 10^5$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	229
1,2-Dichloroethane	265
Dichloromethane	251
DMSO	762
Acetone	235
Dimethylformamide	394
Butanone	173
Nitrobenzene	294
Benzene	91.4
Cyclohexane	8.55
Toluene	67.2
Acetophenone	310
Tetrahydrofurane	120
Tetra-Butyl alcohol	95.0
Dioxane	123
1,2-Dimethoxyethane	64.2
Acetic acid	52.8
Ethyl acetate	90.2
Carbon disulfide	33.3

The entropies and enthalpies of the activation of the oxidation of twenty-four benzyl alcohols exhibited satisfactory correlation ($r^2 = 0.9902$). The value of isokinetic temperature is 585 ± 11 K. The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion¹⁶. The Exner's plot between the values of $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K, for the twenty-four alcohols, is linear (slope = 0.8183 ± 0.0048 ; $r^2 = 0.9996$). The value of isokinetic temperature, determined by Exner's method, is 599 ± 17 K. The two values showed an excellent agreement. A linear isokinetic relationship is, however, a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships¹⁶. It also implies that all the reactions, so correlated, follow a similar mechanism.

B IDC seems to be an ionic compound as a result of proton transfer. To find out the state of B IDC in our reaction conditions, conductivity measurements have been carried out. It was observed that DMSO has very low conductivity and the addition of B IDC in DMSO shows negligible change in the conductivity value. Therefore, B IDC can be considered to be remained as non-ionised under our reaction conditions and does not dissociate as dichromate and benzimidazolium ions. No effect of added benzimidazolium

ion on the rate of oxidation also supports the postulation that B IDC remain as non-ionised¹⁴. The crystal structure study of B IDC, reported by Meng *et al.*¹⁷ supports the non-ionic nature of the oxidant in the reaction system. The dichromate ion connects two benzimidazolium rings via hydrogen bonds. With the effective hydrogen donor (N-H) and hydrogen acceptor (O) in the molecule, B IDC forms a number of hydrogen bonds. Furthermore, an intermolecular hydrogen bridge is remarkably formed between two neighbored dichromate ions. The molecules are then linked into infinite chains by these hydrogen bridges which controlled the releasing process of dichromate ions to reaction system and thus the compound behaves as non-ionic in our reaction system¹⁷.

The data recorded in Table 5 indicate that the correlation of rate constants of oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered as the complete range of the solvent parameters are not available), in terms of linear solvation energy relationship (LSER) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁸ explained ca. 86% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹⁹ the correlations were insignificant.

$$\log k_2 = A + p\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta \quad (3)$$

Here π^* represents the solvent polarity for solvent-solute interaction of non-specific type, β is a scale of solvent hydrogen-bond acceptor basicity, while α represents the solvent hydrogen-bond donor acidity; A is the intercept term.

The data on solvent effect were then analysed in terms of Swain's²⁰ equation, where A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power; C is the intercept term, and $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity.

$$\log k = aA + bB + C \quad (4)$$

The results of the correlation analyses in terms of Swain's equation, individually with A and B , and with $(A + B)$ are given below.

$$\log k_2 = 0.73 \pm 0.02 A + 1.68 \pm 0.01 B - 4.18 \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9993, \text{sd} = 0.01, n = 19, \psi = 0.03$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.49 \pm 0.55 A - 3.02 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0438, \text{sd} = 0.45, n = 19, \psi = 1.00$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.62 \pm 0.13 B - 3.94 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9032, \text{sd} = 0.14, n = 19, \psi = 0.32$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.36 \pm 0.12 (A + B) - 4.15 \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8803, \text{sd} = 0.16, n = 19, \psi = 0.36$$

The data on solvent effect showed an excellent correlation in terms of Swain's equation with both anion- and cation-solvating powers contributing to the observed solvent effect. However, the role of cation-solvation is major. It alone accounts for *ca.* 90% of the data. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$ accounted for *ca.* 88% of the data. In view of the fact *ca.* 88% of the data is accounted by $(A+B)$, an attempt was made to correlate the data with relative permittivity of the solvents. A plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of relative permittivity, however, is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5307$).

The rates of the *para*- and *meta*-compounds, at 298 K, failed to exhibit a significant correlation in terms of Hammett²¹ or Brown's²² substituent constants.

$$\log k_2 = -1.98 \pm 0.14 \sigma - 2.36 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8972; \text{sd} = 0.20; n = 24; \psi = 0.33$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.30 \pm 0.13 \sigma^+ - 2.65 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8300; \text{sd} = 0.27; n = 22; \psi = 0.42$$

The data of *m*-OPh and *m*-NHAc were not included in the above correlation, since σ^+ values were not available.

The rates of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols were subjected to analyses in terms of dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations of Taft²³ and Swain *et al.*²⁴. The rates of oxidation of the *para*- and *meta*-compounds were separately correlated with σ_I and four different σ_R values in Taft's equation²³ and with the field and resonance substituent constants of Swain *et al.*²⁴. The results are summarized in Table 6.

Both the *meta*- and *para*-series of substituted benzyl alcohols meet the requirement of minimum number of substituents for analysis by DSP equations²⁴.

The rates of oxidation of the *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols show an excellent correlation with Taft's σ_I and σ_R^{BA} values. Comparison showed that ψ is smaller for the σ_R^{BA} scale than for the other scales by factors of *ca.* 6 to 27. Thus it is apparent that the rates of oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols by BDC correlate best with σ_I and σ_R^{BA} . However, the rates for the *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols show an excellent correlation with σ_I and σ_R^0 . The reaction constants and statistical data at various temperatures are given in Table 7.

The value of λ^P (*ca.* 1.25) showed that the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is more susceptible to the resonance effect than to the field effect. In the reaction of the *meta*-substituted compounds, however, the value of λ^m is *ca.* 0.72, indicating the greater importance of the field effect. In both the cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature. This showed a decrease in selectivity with an increase in the temperature.

Mechanism: The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The negative values of the polar reaction constants point to an electron-deficient reaction centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. This postulation is supported by the analyses of the solvent effect indicating much more contribution of the cation-solva-

Table 6. Correlation of rate constants of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols with dual-substituent parameters

Subst.	ρ_I	ρ_R	R^2	sd	ψ	n^a
<i>para</i> -Substituted						
σ_I, σ_R^0	-1.44 ± 0.07	-2.40 ± 0.11	0.9828	0.08	0.14	12
σ_I, σ_R^{BA}	-1.52 ± 0.01	-1.92 ± 0.01	0.9996	0.01	0.02	12
σ_I, σ_R^-	-1.14 ± 0.28	-1.29 ± 0.35	0.7028	0.34	0.60	11 ^b
σ_I, σ_R^+	-1.58 ± 0.12	-1.11 ± 0.09	0.9513	0.14	0.24	12
Swain <i>et al.</i> ^c	-0.56 ± 0.05	-0.59 ± 0.04	0.9676	0.11	0.20	12
<i>meta</i> -Substituted						
σ_I, σ_R^0	-2.23 ± 0.01	-1.65 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.01	0.01	13
σ_I, σ_R^{BA}	-2.23 ± 0.07	-1.11 ± 0.07	0.9834	0.08	0.14	13
σ_I, σ_R^-	-2.03 ± 0.21	-1.05 ± 0.25	0.8690	0.25	0.40	11 ^d
σ_I, σ_R^+	-2.21 ± 0.12	-0.60 ± 0.06	0.9533	0.14	0.24	13
Swain <i>et al.</i> ^c	-1.06 ± 0.06	-0.41 ± 0.04	0.9523	0.14	0.24	13

^aTemperature 288 K, *sd* = standard deviation, σ_I and σ_R values are from Ref. 17; ^bDatum for NHCOME not considered; no σ_R^- value is available;

^cField and resonance substituent constants are from Ref. 18; ^dData for NHCOME and OPh not considered; no σ_R^- values are available.

ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 7.89 g (92%) and 6.86 g (80%) respectively, indicating the amount of benzaldehyde formed is about 3.0–3.1 g. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of benzaldehyde. The identity of the DNP was confirmed by the elemental analysis also. The observed values were C, 54.79%; H, 3.40% and N, 19.39%, the calculated values for $C_{13}H_{10}N_4O_4$ are C, 54.55%; H, 3.50% and N, 19.58%. In similar experiments, with the other substituted benzyl alcohols the yields of DNP, after recrystallization, were in the range of 75–88%. Cr^{VI} is reduced to Cr^{III} .

Stoichiometry: To determine the stoichiometry, BDC (0.005 mol) and benzyl alcohol (0.001–0.003 mol) were made up to 100 ml in DMSO in the presence of 1.0 mol dm^{-3} TsOH. The reaction was allowed to stand for ca. 20 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The residual BDC was determined spectrophotometrically at 364 nm. Several determinations, with differently substituted benzyl alcohols, with their different concentrations showed that the stoichiometry is 3:2 i.e. three moles of alcohol are consumed by 2 moles of oxidant. The results with benzyl alcohol are presented in Table 8. BDC thus acts as a 3-electron oxidant and is reduced to Cr^{III} .

Table 8. Stoichiometry of the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by BDC

$10^3[BDC]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3[\text{Benzyl alcohol}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3[\text{Residual BDC}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	[Sulfide]/ [Consumed BDC]
5.0	1.0	4.32	1.47
5.0	2.0	3.71	1.55
5.0	3.0	3.01	1.51
Mean = 1.51 ± 0.04			

Kinetic measurements: Pseudo-first order conditions were attained by keeping a large excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the alcohol over the oxidant. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1 \text{ K}$). The solvent was DMSO, unless stated otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of BDC at 364 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots of $\log [BDC]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The specific rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation:

$k_2 = k_{obs}/[\text{alcohol}]$, in the absence of acid. In correlation analysis, we have used coefficient of determination (C^2 or c^2), standard deviation (sd) and Exner's Parameter¹⁸, ψ , as the measures of the goodness of fit.

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